

CYBERSECURITY AWARENESS AMONG COLLEGE STUDENTS: IMPLICATIONS FOR DIGITAL LITERACY AND PREVENTIVE EDUCATION PROGRAMS

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ABSTRACT

This study assessed the cybersecurity awareness and engagement in risky online behaviors among 573 college students of Metro Dumaguete College (MDC) selected through purposive sampling, focusing only on students with relevant knowledge and exposure to online platforms. The respondents were drawn from various programs, including BTVTED, Criminology, BSBA, Tourism Management, BSIT, and BSCS. The study examined three dimensions of cybersecurity awareness: knowledge of cybersecurity principles, attitudes toward online safety, and actual cybersecurity practices and their relationship to students' involvement in risky online behaviors across three domains: password management, sharing of personal or sensitive information, and conducting transactions over unsecured networks. Results revealed that students generally displayed high to very high levels of cybersecurity awareness. However, moderate levels of risky behaviors persisted, particularly in password-related practices. Significant relationships were found between students' cybersecurity knowledge and attitudes and their risky behaviors involving the sharing of personal information and the use of public Wi-Fi, while no significant association was observed with password management behaviors. Furthermore, a significant difference in risky behaviors was noted across academic programs and year levels, with certain majors, such as Criminology, showing higher engagement in cybersecurity-risk activities. In contrast, no significant differences were observed when grouped according to frequency of internet use. Overall, the findings highlight the need for targeted cybersecurity education and

policy reinforcement within the institution to address persisting vulnerabilities among students.

Keywords: *cybersecurity, awareness, digital literacy, preventive education*

INTRODUCTION

As digital technologies become part of everyday life, cybersecurity awareness has become an essential aspect of digital literacy. Recent studies highlight that university students, despite their frequent online presence, often exhibit limited understanding of cybersecurity risks. For instance, a study by Bottyán (2023) found that university students' awareness levels were inconsistent, with significant gaps in areas like password management and safe online practices. Similarly, research in Mogadishu universities revealed that students' awareness varied significantly, with some institutions reporting higher incidences of cyber threats among their students (Ahmed et al., 2023).

In the Philippines, the integration of digital technologies in education has underscored the need for enhanced cybersecurity awareness among students. A study conducted at Core Gateway College in San Jose City assessed the cybersecurity awareness of college students in response to rising cyber-attack threats. The research indicated that, despite advancements in legislation, Filipino students remain vulnerable to cyber threats, with even Computer Science students falling victim to cyber-attacks (Alabab et al., 2023). Furthermore, a multiple case study of cybersecurity threats and challenges in selected Philippine State Universities and Colleges revealed that user education and cloud security were significant challenges in addressing cybersecurity issues within academic institutions (De Ramos & Esponilla, 2022).

While existing studies provide valuable insights into the state of cybersecurity awareness among students, several gaps remain unaddressed. Notably, there is a lack of comprehensive research focusing on the interplay between students' knowledge, attitudes, and online behaviors concerning cybersecurity. Additionally, limited studies have explored the effectiveness of targeted educational interventions in enhancing cybersecurity awareness and practices among college students. A recent study emphasized the importance of integrating comprehensive cybersecurity awareness programs within higher education to improve students' preparedness against evolving cyber threats (De Ramos & Esponilla, 2022).

Given the increasing prevalence of cyber threats and their potential impact on students' academic and personal lives, it is imperative to assess and enhance cybersecurity awareness among college students. This study aims to bridge existing research gaps by examining the relationship between students' cybersecurity knowledge, attitudes, and online behaviors. By fostering a culture of cybersecurity awareness, this research aligns with the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goal 4 (Quality Education), which emphasizes the importance of inclusive and equitable quality education and promoting lifelong learning opportunities for all. Ultimately, this study seeks to

contribute to the development of targeted preventive education programs that empower students to navigate the digital world safely and responsibly.

Research Questions

With the growing role of digital technology in both school and daily life, cybersecurity awareness became a key part of digital literacy, especially for college students who spent much of their time online. As cyber threats grew more frequent and sophisticated, students needed not only technical skills but also the right attitudes and habits to stay safe online.

This study assessed the level of cybersecurity awareness among MDC college students and examined how their knowledge, attitudes, and online behaviors affected their vulnerability or resilience to cyber threats. The findings aimed to inform the development of educational programs and institutional strategies to strengthen digital literacy and promote safer online practices. Specifically, this study aims to address the following research problems:

1. What is the current level of cybersecurity awareness among college students in terms of:
 - 1.1. Knowledge of cybersecurity principles and threats;
 - 1.2. Attitudes toward cybersecurity and personal responsibility; and
 - 1.3. Actual cybersecurity practices and behaviors?
2. To what extent do college students engage in risky online behaviors that may result from insufficient cybersecurity awareness, particularly in the following areas:
 - 2.1. Password creation and management;
 - 2.2. Sharing of personal or sensitive data online; and
 - 2.3. Conducting online transactions over public or unsecured Wi-Fi networks?
3. How prevalent are specific online behaviors among students that pose cybersecurity risks, such as:
 - 3.1. Sharing of passwords with others;
 - 3.2. Clicking on unknown or suspicious links; and
 - 3.3. Responding to phishing attempts or fraud communications?
4. To what extent do college students rely on various sources of cybersecurity information in terms of:
 - 4.1 Information provided by academic institutions (e.g., courses, seminars, or campus IT policies);
 - 4.2 Content accessed through social media platforms;
 - 4.3 Online discussion forums and community-based platforms ; and
 - 4.4 Peer networks, including classmates, friends, or informal peer advice?
5. Is there a significant relationship between college students 'level of cybersecurity awareness and their engagement in risky online behaviors?
6. Is there a significant difference in students 'engagement in cybersecurity-risk

behaviors when grouped according to the following demographic and usage factors:

- 6.1 Course or major;
- 6.2 Year level; and
- 6.3 Frequency of internet usage?

METHODOLOGY

Research design. This study used a quantitative descriptive-correlational approach. The descriptive part aimed to understand the level of cybersecurity awareness among college students, giving a clear picture of what they know, how they think, and how they behave online. The correlational part looked at how students' awareness connects to their engagement in risky online behaviors. It also explored how factors like course, year level, and how often they use the internet relate to their cybersecurity knowledge, attitudes, and online habits. This approach helped capture both the students' current awareness and the factors that may influence their online safety.

Research respondent. The study was conducted at Metro Dumaguete College (MDC) and involved college students from various programs, including CCSIT, Tourism, Financial and Marketing Management, Criminology, and BTVTEd, across different year levels. Purposive sampling was employed to select participants who were most relevant to the study, ensuring they had sufficient exposure to online environments and could provide meaningful insights into cybersecurity awareness. The study included a total of 573 respondents, which helped ensure that the findings were both reliable and representative of the targeted student groups.

Research instrument. A structured, modified survey questionnaire was employed to assess students' cybersecurity knowledge, attitudes, and online practices. The items were carefully adapted from the validated scales used in the study by Bognar & Bottyan, (2024) to ensure their relevance to the local context. Prior to administration, the questionnaire was thoroughly reviewed and validated by experts in research methodology and Information Technology (IT) to ensure that it was clear, accurate, and appropriate for the target participants.

RESULTS

Table 1.1
Level of Cybersecurity Awareness among College Students in terms of their Knowledge of Cybersecurity Principles and Threats

Statements	\bar{WX}	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
1. I know how to spot fake emails or messages that try to trick me into giving personal information (phishing).	4.01	Agree	High

2. I understand why using long and hard-to-guess passwords is important.	4.47	Strongly Agree	Very High
3. I can name some common online threats like viruses, fake websites, or people pretending to be someone else.	3.61	Agree	High
4. I know that antivirus software and two-step verification help keep my devices and accounts safe.	4.26	Strongly Agree	Very High
5. I understand that posting personal information (like my full name, birthday, or school ID) on public websites or social media can be risky.	4.42	Strongly Agree	Very High
Composite	4.16	Agree	High
Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent	
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High	
3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High	
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate	
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low	
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low	

Table 1.1 shows that the college students have a high level of cybersecurity awareness in terms of their knowledge of cybersecurity principles and threats, as reflected by the composite mean of 4.16. This indicates that, overall, students are generally knowledgeable about safe online practices and common cyber risks.

Table 1.2
Level of Cybersecurity Awareness among College Students in terms of their Attitudes Toward Cybersecurity and Personal Responsibility

Statements	\bar{WX}	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
1. I believe it is my job to protect my own online accounts and information.	4.60	Strongly Agree	Very High
2. I take online safety seriously whenever I use my phone, laptop, or any device connected to the internet.	4.43	Strongly Agree	Very High
3. I believe all students should learn how to stay safe online.	4.52	Strongly Agree	Very High
4. I think it is important to keep apps and software on my devices updated.	4.33	Strongly Agree	Very High
5. I feel uncomfortable when websites or apps ask for too much personal information.	4.27	Strongly Agree	Very High
Composite	4.43	Strongly Agree	Very High
Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent	
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High	
3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High	
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate	
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low	
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low	

Table 1.2 shows that college students have a very high level of cybersecurity awareness in terms of their attitudes toward cybersecurity and personal responsibility, as indicated by the composite mean of 4.43. This means students strongly recognize the importance of protecting their personal information and maintaining safe online practices.

Table 1.3
Level of Cybersecurity Awareness among College Students in terms of their Actual Cybersecurity Practices and Behaviors

Statements	\bar{WX}	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
1. I keep my phone, laptop, and apps updated with the latest version.	4.17	Agree	High
2. I use different passwords for different accounts (like email, social media, school portal).	4.05	Agree	High
3. I avoid clicking on links or downloading files from people or websites I do not trust.	4.33	Strongly Agree	Very High
4. I turn on extra protection for my accounts, like getting a code on my phone (two-step verification).	4.36	Strongly Agree	Very High
5. I do not share my passwords or personal details with anyone, even family, friends or classmates.	4.48	Strongly Agree	Very High
Composite	4.28	Strongly Agree	Very High

Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Table 1.3 indicates that college students demonstrate a very high level of cybersecurity awareness in terms of their actual online safety practices, as reflected in the composite mean of 4.28. This reflects that students consistently engage in secure digital habits, such as updating devices, using protective features, and safeguarding personal information.

Table 2.1
Extent to Which College Students Engage in Risky Online Behaviors Due to Insufficient Cybersecurity Awareness, Particularly in Password Creation and Management

Statements	\bar{WX}	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
1. I use the same password for many of my online accounts.	3.24	Moderately Agree	Moderate

2. I use short or simple passwords that are easy to remember, like “123456” or “password”.	2.62	Moderately Agree	Moderate
3. I rarely or never change my passwords unless I am forced to.	3.39	Moderately Agree	Moderate
4. I write down my passwords on paper or save them in my phone’s notes without a password lock.	3.23	Moderately Agree	Moderate
5. I do not use extra security features like two-factor authentication (getting a code sent to my phone or email).	2.69	Moderately Agree	Moderate
Composite	3.03	Moderately Agree	Moderate

Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Table 2.1 reflects that college students exhibit a moderate level of engagement in risky online behaviors related to password creation and management, as indicated by the composite mean of 3.03. This indicates that while students are somewhat aware of good password practices, many still rely on unsafe habits such as reusing passwords, using simple combinations, and neglecting additional security features.

Table 2.2
Extent to Which College Students Engage in Risky Online Behaviors Due to Insufficient Cybersecurity Awareness, particularly in the Sharing of Personal or Sensitive Data Online

Statements	\bar{wx}	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
1. I sometimes post my full name, birthday, school, or contact information on social media.	2.86	Moderately Agree	Moderate
2. I share photos, videos, or information online without checking who can see them.	2.77	Moderately Agree	Moderate
3. I sometimes give my personal details (like ID number or address) to websites or apps without checking if they are safe.	2.39	Disagree	Low
4. I respond to unknown messages or emails asking for private information.	2.22	Disagree	Low
5. I allow apps to access my contacts, location, or camera without reading the permissions.	2.50	Disagree	Low
Composite	2.55	Disagree	Low

Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
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4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Table 2.2 shows that college students exhibit a low level of risky behavior when it comes to sharing personal or sensitive information online, as indicated by the composite mean of 2.55. This indicates that students are generally cautious about disclosing private data, although occasional lapses, such as posting information on social media, still occur.

Table 2.3
Extent to Which College Students Engage in Risky Online Behaviors Due to Insufficient Cybersecurity Awareness, particularly in Conducting Online Transactions over Public or Unsecured Wi-Fi Networks

Statements	\bar{wx}	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
1. I connect to free public Wi-Fi (like in cafes, malls, or terminals) without checking if it's secure.	3.09	Moderately Agree	Moderate
2. I use public Wi-Fi to log in to my online banking or shop using my credit/debit card.	2.43	Disagree	Low
3. I do not use a VPN (Virtual Private Network) or other secure methods when using public internet.	2.86	Moderately Agree	Moderate
4. I trust that public Wi-Fi is always safe to use for anything online.	2.67	Moderately Agree	Moderate
5. I never check if a website is secure (like looking for "https" or a padlock symbol) before entering personal or payment details	2.58	Disagree	Low
Composite	2.73	Moderately Agree	Moderate

Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Table 2.3 indicates that students display a moderate level of risky behavior when conducting online transactions over public or unsecured Wi-Fi networks, with a composite mean of 2.73. While some students take precautions, many still engage in unsafe practices like connecting to unsecured networks or neglecting to verify website security.

Table 3.1***Online Behaviors among Students that Pose Cybersecurity Risks, such as Sharing of Passwords with Others***

Statements	\bar{WX}	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
1. I have shared my password with a friend, classmate, or family member.	2.20	Disagree	Low
3. I gave my school portal password to someone to help me with assignments or enrollment.	2.15	Disagree	Low
2. I let others log in to my accounts (like email or social media) using my password.	2.13	Disagree	Low
4. I believe it is okay to share passwords with people I trust.	2.31	Disagree	Low
5. I saved my passwords on a shared device or in a place where others can see them.	2.10	Disagree	Low
Composite	2.18	Disagree	Low

Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Table 3.1 indicates that college students demonstrate a low level of risky online behavior related to sharing passwords, as reflected by the composite mean of 2.18. This shows that students are generally cautious about keeping their account credentials private and avoid practices that could compromise their online security

Table 3.2***Online Behaviors among Students that Pose Cybersecurity Risks, such as Clicking on Unknown or Suspicious Links***

Statements	\bar{WX}	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
1. I have clicked on links from messages or emails without knowing who sent them.	2.20	Disagree	Low
2. I sometimes open links in group chats or social media without checking if they are safe.	2.53	Disagree	Low
3. I have visited websites that looked unusual or asked for personal information unexpectedly.	2.45	Disagree	Low
4. I rarely check the full website address before clicking a link.	2.80	Moderately Agree	Moderate
5. I have clicked on ads or pop-ups that promised rewards, free items, or giveaways.	2.39	Disagree	Low

Composite **2.47** **Disagree** **Low**

Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Table 3.2 shows that college students exhibit a low level of risky online behavior when it comes to clicking on unknown or suspicious links, as indicated by the composite mean of 2.47. This indicates that students are generally careful about interacting with potentially unsafe links, although occasional oversights such as not fully checking website addresses still occur in moderate level.

Table 3.3
Online Behaviors among Students that Pose Cybersecurity Risks, such as Responding to Phishing Attempts or Fraud Communications

Statements	\bar{WX}	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
1. I have replied to emails or messages that later turned out to be scams.	2.31	Disagree	Low
2. I once gave personal information (like name, birthday, or student ID) in response to a suspicious message.	2.27	Disagree	Low
3. Sometimes, I believed messages that said “I won a prize” or had to verify my account right away.	2.21	Disagree	Low
4. I have downloaded files or apps from links sent by unknown senders.	2.16	Disagree	Low
5. I find it hard to tell whether a message is real or a scam	2.51	Disagree	Low
Composite	2.29	Disagree	Low

Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Table 3.3 indicates that college students demonstrate a low level of risky online behavior in responding to phishing attempts or fraudulent communications, as reflected by the composite mean of 2.29. This implies that students generally exercise caution when handling suspicious messages, although some uncertainty in identifying scams still exists.

Table 4.1***Extent to which College Students rely on Various Sources of Cybersecurity Information, including Information provided by Academic Institutions (e.g., Courses, Seminars, or Campus IT Policies)***

Statements	\bar{w}_x	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
1. I have attended school-organized seminars or webinars about online safety or cybersecurity.	3.54	Agree	High
2. I learned about cybersecurity through subjects or lessons taught in my college courses.	3.81	Agree	High
3. I read and follow the school's IT policies or online security guidelines.	3.93	Agree	High
4. I rely on campus resources (e.g., IT department or helpdesk) when I need cybersecurity advice.	3.61	Agree	High
5. I believe that my school gives useful and reliable information about how to stay safe online.	4.02	Agree	High
Composite	3.78	Agree	High

Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Table 4.1 shows that college students have a high level of reliance on academic institutions as sources of cybersecurity information, with a composite mean of 3.78. This indicates that students actively utilize school-provided resources such as courses, seminars, IT policies, and campus support services to enhance their knowledge and practices in online safety

Table 4.2***Extent to which College Students rely on Various Sources of Cybersecurity Information, including Content Accessed through Social Media Platforms***

Statements	\bar{w}_x	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
1. I watch or follow pages/accounts on social media that give tips about online safety and cybersecurity.	3.92	Agree	High
2. I learn about internet scams, hacking, or online threats through posts or videos on social media.	3.78	Agree	High
3. I usually believe the cybersecurity information I see on social media.	3.73	Agree	High
4. I share or repost cybersecurity-related content that I see on my feed.	3.42	Agree	High
5. I prefer getting information about cybersecurity through short videos or posts on social media.	3.58	Agree	High

Composite	3.69	Agree	High
Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent	
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High	
3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High	
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate	
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low	
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low	

Table 4.2 indicates that college students exhibit a high level of reliance on social media as a source of cybersecurity information, reflected by the composite mean of 3.69. This suggests that students frequently access, trust, and share cybersecurity content on social platforms to stay informed about online safety practices and potential threats

Table 4.3
Extent to which College Students rely on Various Sources of Cybersecurity Information, including Online Discussion Forums and Community-Based Platforms (e.g., Reddit, Quora, Stack Exchange, etc.)

Statements	\bar{wx}	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
1. I read online discussions or Q&A forums when I want to learn how to protect myself online.	3.88	Agree	High
2. I trust the cybersecurity advice I find in community posts or forums.	3.81	Agree	High
3. I have asked questions about online security or privacy on public forums or groups.	3.66	Agree	High
4. I follow discussion threads where people share news or tips about internet threats.	3.73	Agree	High
5. I rely on real experiences shared by others in online forums to guide my online behavior.	3.72	Agree	High
Composite	3.76	Agree	High
Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent	
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High	
3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High	
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate	
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low	
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low	

Table 4.3 shows that college students demonstrate a high level of reliance on online discussion forums and community-based platforms for cybersecurity information, as indicated by the composite mean of 3.76. This implies that students actively engage with and trust advice, shared experiences, and discussions in online communities to improve their online safety practices.

Table 4.4

Extent to which College Students rely on Various Sources of Cybersecurity Information, including Peer Networks (e.g., classmates, friends, informal peer advice)

Statements	\bar{wx}	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
1. I ask my friends or classmates when I have questions about online safety or account security.	3.72	Agree	High
2. I follow cybersecurity tips that my peers share with me (e.g., in chat groups or face-to-face).	3.69	Agree	High
3. I often hear about scams, threats, or hacking incidents from other students.	3.79	Agree	High
4. I rely on peer recommendations when choosing apps, security tools, or browser settings.	3.67	Agree	High
5. I learn more about how to stay safe online through casual conversations with friends than from official sources	3.72	Agree	High
Composite	3.72	Agree	High
Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent	
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High	
3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High	
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate	
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low	
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low	

Table 4.4 indicates that college students show a high level of reliance on peer networks for cybersecurity information, as reflected by the composite mean of 3.72. This shows that students frequently consult friends and classmates, trust their advice, and share experiences to guide their online safety practices

Table 5 presents the relationship between college students' level of cybersecurity awareness and their engagement in risky online behaviors. The results indicate that students' knowledge of cybersecurity principles and their attitudes toward cybersecurity and personal responsibility are significantly related to risky behaviors involving the sharing of personal or sensitive information online and conducting transactions over public or unsecured Wi-Fi networks. Conversely, no significant relationship was found between students' cybersecurity awareness and risky behaviors related to password creation and management or actual cybersecurity practices, indicating that awareness does not always translate into safe behavioral habits in these areas.

Table 5
Significant Relationship between College Students 'Level of cybersecurity Awareness and their Engagement in Risky Online Behaviors

Variables Correlated	r	p-value	Decision	Remark
Knowledge of Cybersecurity Principles and Threats				
Password Creation and Management	-0.032	0.439	Failed to Reject H ₀₁	Not Significant
Sharing of Personal or Sensitive Data Online	0.130	0.002	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Conducting Online Transactions over Public or Unsecured Wi-Fi Networks	0.131	0.002	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Attitudes toward Cybersecurity and Personal Responsibility				
Password Creation and Management	0.011	0.791	Failed to Reject H ₀₁	Not Significant
Sharing of Personal or Sensitive Data Online	0.137	0.001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Conducting Online Transactions over Public or Unsecured Wi-Fi Networks	0.100	0.016	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Actual Cybersecurity Practices and Behaviors				
Password Creation and Management	-0.025	0.543	Failed to Reject H ₀₁	Not Significant
Sharing of Personal or Sensitive Data Online	-0.056	0.179	Failed to Reject H ₀₁	Not Significant
Conducting Online Transactions over Public or Unsecured Wi-Fi Networks	-0.036	0.395	Failed to Reject H ₀₁	Not Significant

Table 6.1 shows that there is a significant difference in students' engagement in cybersecurity-risk behaviors based on their course or major. Specifically, behaviors such as sharing passwords, clicking on unknown or suspicious links, and responding to phishing or fraudulent messages vary significantly across programs, with some majors exhibiting higher engagement in risky practices than others. For instance, Criminology students exhibited higher engagement in risky behaviors such as sharing passwords, clicking on unknown links, and responding to phishing messages compared to other programs. This highlights the influence of academic discipline on students' online safety habits.

Table 6.1
Significant Difference in Students' Engagement in Cybersecurity-Risk Behaviors when grouped according to Course or Major

Variables	n	Mean	F	p	Decision	Remark
Sharing of Passwords with Others						
(1) BTVTED	34	2.888				
(2) BSTM	88	3.286				
(3) BSBA (MM & FM)	47	3.140	7.53	0.001	Reject H ₀₂	Significant
(4) BS CS & IT	270	2.835				
(5) CRIMINOLOGY	134	3.267				
Clicking on Unknown or Suspicious Links						
(1) BTVTED	34	2.371				
(2) BSTM	88	2.809				
(3) BSBA (MM & FM)	47	2.443	8.29	0.001	Reject H ₀₂	Significant
(4) BS CS & IT	270	2.330				
(5) CRIMINOLOGY	134	2.897				
Responding to Phishing Attempts or Fraud Communications						
(1) BTVTED	34	2.288				
(2) BSTM	88	2.959				
(3) BSBA (MM & FM)	47	2.587	8.27	0.001	Reject H ₀₂	Significant
(4) BS CS & IT	270	2.564				
(5) CRIMINOLOGY	134	3.058				

Table 6.2 shows that there is a significant difference in students' engagement in sharing passwords when grouped according to year level, with 4th-year students exhibiting higher engagement in this risky behavior compared to other year levels. However, differences in behaviors such as clicking on unknown links or responding to phishing attempts were not statistically significant across year levels, indicating that these risks are relatively consistent regardless of academic standing.

Table 6.2
Significant Difference in Students' Engagement in Cybersecurity-Risk Behaviors when grouped according to Year Level

Variables	n	Mean	F	p	Decision	Remark
Sharing of Passwords with Others						
(1) 1 st Year	136	2.899	3.87	0.009	Reject H ₀₂	Significant

(2) 2 nd Year	290	3.004				
(3) 3 rd Year	5	2.560				
(4) 4 th Year	142	3.239				
Clicking on Unknown or Suspicious Links						
(1) 1 st Year	136	2.410	1.82	0.143	Failed to Reject H ₀₂	Not Significant
(2) 2 nd Year	290	2.588				
(3) 3 rd Year	5	1.840				
(4) 4 th Year	142	2.623				
Responding to Phishing Attempts or Fraud Communications						
(1) 1 st Year	136	2.647	2.22	0.085	Failed to Reject H ₀₂	Not Significant
(2) 2 nd Year	290	2.690				
(3) 3 rd Year	5	2.120				
(4) 4 th Year	142	2.896				

Table 6.3
Significant Difference in Students' Engagement in Cybersecurity-Risk Behaviors when grouped according to Frequency of Internet Usage

Variables	n	F	p	Decision	Remark
Sharing of Passwords with Others					
(1) 1 hour – 20 hours	161	1.59	0.054	Failed to Reject H ₀₂	Not Significant
Clicking on Unknown or Suspicious Links					
(1) 1 hour – 20 hours	161	1.34	0.151	Failed to Reject H ₀₂	Not Significant
Responding to Phishing Attempts or Fraud Communications					
(1) 1 hour – 20 hours	161	1.35	0.145	Failed to Reject H ₀₂	Not Significant

Table 6.3 shows that there is no significant difference in students' engagement in cybersecurity-risk behaviors when grouped according to frequency of internet usage. This indicates that the amount of time students spend online does not significantly influence their likelihood of sharing passwords, clicking on suspicious links, or responding to phishing attempts.

DISCUSSION

The level of cybersecurity awareness among college students

1.1. Knowledge of cybersecurity principles, risks, and threats

Table 1.1 shows that students possess a high level of cybersecurity awareness (M = 4.16), particularly in understanding strong passwords (M = 4.47), protecting personal information (M = 4.42), and recognizing the value of antivirus tools and two-factor authentication (M = 4.26). However, their ability to identify specific threats (M = 3.61) is comparatively weaker, suggesting gaps in practical threat-recognition skills. This indicates that while foundational knowledge is strong, students may still struggle to detect real-world cyber risks. Recent studies confirm this pattern: Alqahtani (2022) and Du (2023) highlight that cybersecurity awareness is multi-dimensional, requiring targeted instruction in threat identification, while Okokpujie *et al.* (2023) found that students remain vulnerable to phishing despite high self-reported awareness. These findings suggest that MDC students, like many others, would benefit from applied, behavior-focused training to translate knowledge into effective cybersecurity practices (Altarawneh *et al.*, 2025; Chandarman and Van Niekerk, 2017).

1.2. Attitudes toward cybersecurity, digital safety, and personal responsibility

Table 1.2 shows that students hold very strong cybersecurity attitudes, with a composite mean of 4.43 (“Strongly Agree – Very High”). They view protecting their online accounts as a personal responsibility (M = 4.60), take online safety seriously across devices (M = 4.43), and believe all students should learn about cybersecurity (M = 4.52). They also value keeping software updated (M = 4.33) and are cautious when apps request excessive personal information (M = 4.27). These results indicate that students possess a strong mindset toward responsible digital behavior and data privacy.

However, while positive attitudes often support safer practices, they do not always lead to consistent online behavior. Thus, continuous reinforcement through institutional policies, digital literacy initiatives, and reminders about privacy protection remains important. This result aligns with recent literature: Alqahtani (2022) and Du (2023) found that strong cybersecurity attitudes predict safer digital practices, yet studies like Okokpujie *et al.* (2023) and Chandarman and Van Niekerk (2017) highlight that vulnerabilities, especially in phishing, persist despite strong attitudes. More recent findings by Altarawneh *et al.* (2025) also confirm that positive attitudes increase caution in data sharing but must be paired with practical training. Overall, the results reflect a generally responsible student population that would still benefit from ongoing behavior-focused cybersecurity education.

1.3. Practices and behaviors related to the application of cybersecurity measures

Table 1.3 indicates that students generally demonstrate very high levels of protective online behavior (overall M = 4.28). They most consistently avoid sharing

passwords (M = 4.48), enable extra security measures such as two-factor authentication (M = 4.36), and steer clear of suspicious links (M = 4.33). While they also keep their devices updated (M = 4.17) and use unique passwords (M = 4.05), these behaviors occur slightly less frequently. This suggests that students readily adopt simple, high-impact security actions but are less consistent with practices requiring continuous effort, such as maintaining varied passwords or performing regular device updates.

This result aligns with prior research. Rajivan *et al.* (2020) observed that users often procrastinate routine security tasks, mirroring students' lower tendency to update devices. Wash and Rader (2021) similarly reported that individuals struggle to maintain strong, varied passwords—consistent with the comparatively lower mean for password uniqueness. In contrast, Baraković and Baraković-Husić (2023) found that students more easily adopt straightforward but effective measures like avoiding suspicious links and enabling 2FA, which matches the strongest practices in this study. Additional studies support these findings: Alqahtani (2022) noted that high cybersecurity awareness predicts safer behaviors, while Okokpujie *et al.* (2023) highlighted students' responsiveness to phishing-avoidance cues. Marshall (2024) and Rajivan *et al.* (2020) further emphasized that practical, hands-on interventions particularly those targeting account and email security significantly improve behaviors such as enabling 2FA.

The extent to which college students engage in risky online behaviors may be influenced by their level of cybersecurity awareness

2.1. Password creation and management

The data in Table 2.1 show that MDC college students exhibit a moderate level of risky password practices (M = 3.03), including password reuse, use of simple passwords, infrequent password changes, storing passwords insecurely, and limited use of two-factor authentication. This indicates a clear gap between cybersecurity awareness and actual password-related behavior. Recent studies support this results. Bognár and Bottyán (2024) found that university students consistently show weaknesses in password management despite reporting adequate awareness, aligning with the moderate-risk behaviors observed in the MDC sample. Suleski *et al.* (2023) emphasized that although two-factor authentication significantly improves security, its adoption remains low due to usability and motivational barriers, which mirrors students' moderate tendency to avoid extra security steps. Similarly, Merdenyan and Petrie (2022) reported that risky password behaviors persist because users prioritize convenience over security, explaining why MDC students continue practices like password reuse and storing passwords in unsecured notes. Together, these studies confirm that the MDC findings are not isolated, but part of a broader, documented trend among university populations where awareness does not consistently translate into secure password management.

2.2. Sharing of personal or sensitive data online

Table 2.2 indicates that college students generally engage in low levels of risky online behaviors related to sharing personal or sensitive information, as shown by the composite

mean of 2.55 (Low). Although students moderately agree that they sometimes post personal details such as their full name, birthday, or school on social media (M = 2.86) and share photos or information without checking privacy settings (M = 2.77), they largely avoid more hazardous practices. These include giving personal information to unfamiliar websites or applications (M = 2.39), responding to unknown messages requesting private data (M = 2.22), and granting app permissions without reviewing them (M = 2.50). These findings are consistent with prior research showing that increasing privacy awareness reduces engagement in risky online behaviors. For instance, Liu and Wang (2023) reported that students are becoming more cautious about sharing sensitive data online. Similarly, Abladi and Weir (2020) found that individuals with higher awareness tend to avoid risky disclosure, particularly when threats are obvious. Titi (2025) likewise observed that privacy and security awareness significantly lower the likelihood of providing personal data to untrusted sources. However, the moderate tendencies toward sharing personal information on social media align with findings by Makovkina and Nesterova (2020), who noted that students often underestimate the long-term risks of posting personal content despite general cybersecurity awareness. These results indicate that while students practice caution in handling sensitive information, they still display mild vulnerabilities in everyday online sharing habits

2.3. Conducting online transactions over public or unsecured Wi-Fi networks

Table 2.3 indicates that MDC students exhibit a moderate level of risky behaviors when conducting online transactions over public or unsecured Wi-Fi networks, with a composite mean of 2.73. Students frequently connect to public Wi-Fi without checking security (M = 3.09) and underutilize protective measures such as VPNs (M = 2.86) or verifying website security before submitting personal or payment information (M = 2.58), though they rarely use public Wi-Fi for banking or shopping (M = 2.43). This pattern indicates that convenience often outweighs protective practices, reflecting partial awareness but inconsistent application of cybersecurity measures. These findings align with the study of Namara *et al.* (2020), who reported that users' adoption of VPNs is influenced by convenience and usability factors. Similarly, Sangeen *et al.* (2023) found that individuals often trust public Wi-Fi despite known risks, supporting the observation that students connect to unsecured networks. Pattnaik *et al.* (2023) further highlighted that non-expert users frequently display mixed practices regarding online security on public networks, indicating that knowledge alone does not always translate into safe behavior. Collectively, these studies reinforce the present results, underscoring the need for practical interventions, such as campus VPN promotion, automated security checks, and awareness campaigns, to reduce students' vulnerability during online transactions over public networks

Online behaviors among students that pose cybersecurity risks

3.1. Sharing of passwords with others:

Table 3.1 indicates that MDC students demonstrate a low level of risky online behavior regarding password sharing, as reflected in the composite mean of 2.18

(Disagree – Low). Students rarely share their passwords with friends, classmates, or family (M = 2.20), allow others to access their accounts (M = 2.13), or provide school portal credentials to assist with academic tasks (M = 2.15). They also tend to avoid storing passwords on shared devices (M = 2.10) and generally reject the idea of sharing passwords with trusted individuals (M = 2.31). These results imply that students are generally cautious about maintaining account confidentiality, consistent with prior research indicating that password-sharing behaviors are minimized when users perceive high personal responsibility and cybersecurity awareness (Alqahtani, 2022; Wash & Rader, 2021). However, low but nonzero means suggest occasional lapses, highlighting the need for reinforcement through practical interventions, such as reminders about secure password storage and multi-factor authentication.

3.2. Clicking on unknown or suspicious links

Table 3.2 shows that MDC students exhibit a low level of risky behavior when interacting with unknown or suspicious links, with a composite mean of 2.47 (Disagree – Low). Students rarely click on links from unknown senders in messages or emails (M = 2.20), and only occasionally open links in group chats or social media without verifying safety (M = 2.53). They similarly avoid unusual websites that unexpectedly request personal information (M = 2.45) or clicking on ads and pop-ups promising rewards (M = 2.39). However, checking the full website address before clicking links is somewhat inconsistent (M = 2.80), indicating a moderate lapse in attention to detail. These findings align with previous research indicating that users with higher cybersecurity awareness tend to avoid obvious phishing or suspicious links but may still exhibit minor lapses due to convenience or inattentiveness (Wash & Rader, 2021; Alqahtani, 2022). The results emphasize the need for continued awareness initiatives and brief, practical exercises such as simulated phishing drills to strengthen vigilance in everyday online behavior.

3.3. Responding to phishing attempts or fraud communications

Table 3.3 reflects that MDC students have a low tendency to fall for phishing attempts or fraudulent communications (composite mean = 2.29), rarely responding to scam emails, giving out personal information, or downloading suspicious files. This cautious behavior aligns with findings from Gwenthure (2025), who used the Health Belief Model and found that university students are more likely to perform protective behaviors when they perceive phishing attacks as severe and believe in their ability to defend themselves. Similarly, Du *et al.* (2024) identified barriers, self-efficacy, and past experience as significant determinants of phishing-preventive behavior among students. However, Ahmead *et al.* (2024) noted that even aware undergraduates still engage in other risky behaviors, like sharing personal data, indicating that low phishing susceptibility does not necessarily imply comprehensive risk-free online behavior. These studies reinforce the importance of psychological and experience-based interventions to maintain low phishing risk but also suggest a need for broader cybercrime education

The Extent to which college students rely on various sources of cybersecurity information

4.1 Information provided by academic institutions (e.g., courses, seminars, or campus IT policies)

Table 4.1 shows that MDC students moderately rely on academic institutions as a source of cybersecurity information, with a composite mean of 3.78 (Agree – High). Students frequently report learning through courses (M = 3.81), following IT policies (M = 3.93), and attending school-organized seminars or webinars (M = 3.54). They also moderately rely on campus IT resources when seeking guidance (M = 3.61) and perceive institutional information as reliable (M = 4.02). These findings align with prior research showing that structured academic interventions, such as formal courses, workshops, and accessible IT policies, significantly enhance students' cybersecurity knowledge and responsible practices (Alqahtani, 2022; Du, 2023; Zhou *et al.*, 2023). Nevertheless, while institutional sources provide reliable guidance, students' reliance may not fully translate into consistent safe practices, emphasizing the need for active, hands-on learning opportunities, such as simulations or interactive workshops.

4.2 Content accessed through social media platforms

The results in Table 4.2 reveal that college students rely heavily on social media platforms as sources of cybersecurity information, as reflected in the composite mean of 3.69, interpreted as Agree or High. Students commonly follow pages or accounts that share online safety tips (M = 3.92) and frequently learn about scams, hacking, and other cyber threats through posts or videos they encounter on social media (M = 3.78). Many also tend to trust the cybersecurity information they see on these platforms (M = 3.73), indicating that user-generated content significantly shapes their understanding of online risks. Furthermore, students show active engagement by sharing cybersecurity-related posts (M = 3.42) and demonstrate a preference for short-form content such as videos or brief informational posts (M = 3.58). These findings align with previous studies highlighting that young adults often depend on social media sites like Facebook, TikTok, and YouTube as primary channels for digital safety information (Alshaikh, 2020; Bhatnagar & Pry, 2020; Altarawneh *et al.*, 2025). However, scholars emphasize that social media platforms may also expose users to misinformation, making critical evaluation and media literacy essential components of effective cybersecurity education (Alqurashi *et al.*, 2024; Chowdhury *et al.*, 2023).

4.3 Online discussion forums and community-based platforms

The findings in Table 4.3 indicate that college students rely strongly on online discussion forums and community-based platforms such as Reddit, Quora, and Stack Exchange as sources of cybersecurity information, as shown by the composite mean of 3.76, interpreted as Agree or High. Students frequently read online discussions and Q&A forums to learn how to protect themselves online (M = 3.88) and generally trust the cybersecurity advice posted by community members (M = 3.81). Many students also

actively participate by asking questions about online security (M = 3.66), following discussion threads about emerging internet threats (M = 3.73), and using real experiences shared by other users to guide their own online behavior (M = 3.72). These results support existing literature noting that online forums serve as valuable crowdsourced spaces where individuals learn practical strategies and incident-based knowledge about cybersecurity (Bada & Nurse, 2020; Bosch *et al.*, 2020). Moreover, studies show that peer-generated narratives and experiential posts contribute significantly to users' awareness, sense-making, and risk assessment in digital environments (Fish *et al.*, 2023; Elraya & Jamil, 2023). However, researchers caution that while forums offer diverse insights, they may also circulate unverified advice, underscoring the need for students to evaluate the credibility of user-generated content (Saritepeci *et al.*, 2024).

4.4 Peer networks, including classmates, friends, or informal peer advice

Table 4.4 shows that college students heavily rely on peer networks such as classmates, friends, and informal peer conversations as key sources of cybersecurity information, with a composite mean of 3.72 interpreted as Agree or High. Students frequently consult peers when they have questions about online safety (M = 3.72) and follow cybersecurity tips shared through chat groups or face-to-face interactions (M = 3.69). They also commonly learn about online scams, threats, and hacking incidents from fellow students (M = 3.79), demonstrating that peer communication plays a vital role in shaping cybersecurity awareness. Additionally, students rely on peer recommendations for apps, tools, and settings (M = 3.67) and even report learning more from informal conversations than from official sources (M = 3.72). These findings are consistent with previous research highlighting the influence of peer networks on digital behavior and cybersecurity decision-making, where students often trust advice from individuals they know personally (Van Ouytsel, 2021; Yazdanmehr *et al.*, 2020). Studies have also shown that peer discussions help individuals make sense of digital risks and develop practical strategies to improve their online safety (Herath *et al.*, 2022). However, researchers note that peer-shared information can vary in accuracy, which reinforces the importance of pairing peer-based learning with credible institutional guidance (Redmiles *et al.*, 2020).

Relationship between college students' level of cybersecurity awareness and their engagement in risky online behaviors

Table 5 presents the correlation analysis between college students' level of cybersecurity awareness and their engagement in risky online behaviors. Results reveal a mixed pattern of relationships across awareness dimensions. First, knowledge of cybersecurity principles and threats showed no significant relationship with password creation and management ($r = -.032$, $p = .439$), indicating that knowing cybersecurity concepts does not necessarily translate to safer password habits. This aligns with previous findings that conceptual awareness alone does not always influence password behavior (Mayer *et al.*, 2022). However, significant positive correlations were observed between cybersecurity knowledge and risky behaviors related to sharing personal or sensitive information online ($r = .130$, $p = .002$) and conducting transactions over unsecured Wi-Fi networks ($r = .131$, $p = .002$). These results suggest that even

knowledgeable students may still willingly take risks, supporting literature indicating that awareness does not always override convenience-driven behavior (Redmiles *et al.*, 2020).

Similarly, attitudes toward cybersecurity and personal responsibility did not significantly predict password management behavior ($r = .011$, $p = .791$), reinforcing earlier studies showing that strong attitudes do not always translate into consistent password practices (Fernando *et al.*, 2023). However, attitudes showed significant positive correlations with risky behaviors related to oversharing data ($r = .137$, $p = .001$) and using unsecured Wi-Fi for online transactions ($r = .100$, $p = .016$). These findings suggest that students who perceive themselves as responsible or aware may still underestimate threats in real-world digital contexts, an example of the optimism bias described by Betts *et al.* (2024).

Finally, actual cybersecurity practices and behaviors showed no significant relationship with any of the risky online behaviors assessed, including password management ($r = -.025$, $p = .543$), sharing sensitive data ($r = -.056$, $p = .179$), and unsecured Wi-Fi use ($r = -.036$, $p = .395$). This indicates that students who follow protective practices do not necessarily avoid other forms of risky behavior, supporting prior research suggesting that cybersecurity habits often exist in isolated domains rather than as consistent behavioral patterns (Kizito & Ibebuogu, 2024). These results highlight that cybersecurity awareness whether cognitive, attitudinal, or behavioral, does not uniformly predict safer online behavior. Instead, risky online actions may be influenced by other factors such as convenience, peer norms, or perceived invulnerability.

Difference in students 'engagement in cybersecurity-risk behaviors when grouped according to the following demographic and usage factors

6.1 Course or major

Table 6.1 reveals significant differences in students 'engagement in cybersecurity-risk behaviors across academic programs ($p = .001$). BSTM and Criminology students consistently reported the highest risk levels, whether in password sharing ($M = 3.286$; $M = 3.267$), clicking suspicious links ($M = 2.809$; $M = 2.897$), or responding to phishing attempts ($M = 2.959$; $M = 3.058$). In contrast, BSCS/IT students showed the lowest engagement in these risky behaviors, indicating stronger cybersecurity discipline, likely due to greater technical exposure. This result aligns with prior research showing that students with ICT-related backgrounds are less vulnerable to password misuse and phishing attacks (Albladi & Weir, 2020) and that non-technical majors tend to show higher susceptibility to deceptive online practices (Diaz *et al.*, 2020; Göldağ, 2021). Thus, the findings indicate that cybersecurity risks vary meaningfully by program, emphasizing the need for discipline-specific awareness initiatives.

6.2 Year level

Table 6.2 shows that year level significantly influences students' engagement in password-sharing behaviors ($p = .009$), with 4th-year students exhibiting the highest risk ($M = 3.239$), followed by 2nd-year students ($M = 3.004$). However, no significant differences were found across year levels for clicking suspicious links ($p = .143$) and responding to phishing attempts ($p = .085$), indicating that these risks are relatively consistent regardless of academic progression. The elevated risk among upper-year students may reflect increased academic workload, greater use of shared digital tasks, or complacency developed over time. This trend aligns with findings by Goldag (2021), who reported that digital fatigue can lead to lapses in secure behaviors among older or more experienced students. Similarly, Hong *et al.* (2022) found that college students' cybersecurity habits do not necessarily improve with age or years in school, particularly in phishing-related behaviors. Meanwhile, the uniformity in susceptibility to clicking suspicious links matches findings by Diaz *et al.* (2020), who found that phishing vulnerability remains stable across educational stages. Overall, the results suggest that higher academic standing does not guarantee safer cyber practices, emphasizing the need for continuous cybersecurity reinforcement across all year levels.

6.3 Frequency of internet usage

Table 6.3 shows no significant differences in students' engagement in cybersecurity-risk behaviors when grouped by frequency of internet use (sharing passwords $p = .054$; clicking suspicious links $p = .151$; responding to phishing $p = .145$), indicating that hours spent online do not reliably predict whether students adopt risky cybersecurity behaviors. This result is consistent with research that finds mixed or weak links between mere internet-use duration and security outcomes: some studies report that compulsive or problematic internet use relates to poorer security behavior only when combined with other psychosocial factors (Chen *et al.*, 2021), while broader surveys in developing-country university samples show that demographic and attitudinal variables (rather than simple time-online metrics) better explain cybersecurity posture (Lau *et al.*, 2022). Likewise, Alqahtani (2022) found that specific knowledge domains (password, browser, social media security) predict cybersecurity awareness more strongly than generic measures of online exposure. These studies support the interpretation that time online alone is not a reliable predictor of risky cybersecurity behavior; instead, quality of knowledge, attitudes, self-efficacy, and contextual factors matter more.

Conclusions.

“Awareness alone is not enough; practice ensures safety” (NIST). Consistent with this principle, the study found that MDC college students demonstrate high cybersecurity awareness, yet moderate risky behaviors persist, particularly in password management. While knowledge and attitudes significantly influence risks related to personal data sharing and public Wi-Fi use, they do not fully prevent unsafe password practices. Engagement in risky behaviors also varies by academic major and year level, with Criminology and 4th-year students showing higher risks, whereas internet usage

frequency has no significant effect. These findings underscore the need for targeted, program-specific cybersecurity education and strengthened institutional policies to help students translate awareness into consistent safe online practices.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed to enhance cybersecurity awareness and reduce risky online behaviors among college students:

A. The College Administration and IT Department

1. May organize regular workshops, seminars, and practical exercises on safe password management, recognizing phishing attempts, and secure online transactions, particularly targeting high-risk groups such as Criminology students and 4th-year students.
2. Ensure clear, accessible guidelines, provide tools like two-factor authentication, secure Wi-Fi access, and offer responsive support to encourage safe online practices.
3. Strengthen Institutional Policies and IT Support.

B. Faculty members

1. Faculty members may incorporate cybersecurity topics into relevant courses across all programs, emphasizing hands-on practice and real-life scenarios.

C. Student Affairs Office and Student organizations and Peer Leaders

1. May organize forums on cybersecurity tips and updates, promoting continuous engagement and awareness among students.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study entitled “Cybersecurity Awareness Among College Students: Implications for Digital Literacy and Preventive Education Programs” strictly adhered to ethical principles and guidelines for research involving human participants.

All participants were provided with comprehensive and transparent information regarding the study's objectives, methodologies, and their rights to participate voluntarily. Before administering the questionnaire, we ensured that written informed consent was obtained from each respondent, as clearly outlined in the introductory section of the instrument.

The researchers treated all collected responses with the highest level of confidentiality. No personally identifiable information was disclosed or included in the presentation of the findings. Research data were securely stored and accessible only to the research team. Following the completion of the study's presentation and defense, all survey materials were permanently disposed of through shredding, ensuring the utmost data privacy and integrity.

Moreover, the institution acknowledged the responsible deployment of artificial intelligence technologies to foster academic innovation, enhance research processes, and streamline administrative functions. AI tools were exclusively utilized for language editing and document formatting purposes. The authors retained full ownership of all intellectual contributions and scholarly inputs.

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